

Surface integrity improvement of EDM components by Robotic Micro Abrasive Jet Machining

Sreevalsan S. Menon

PG Student, Dept. of Mech. Engineering
NSS College Engineering
Palakkad, India
ssmenonever@gmail.com

Santhosh Kumar N.

Professor, Dept. of Mech. Engineering
NSS College Engineering
Palakkad, India
skmns@yahoo.com

Abstract— This study investigates the improvement of surface integrity of electrical discharge machined (EDM) components by micro abrasive jet machining with help of a robot. To provide a better surface for spark eroded components, the recast layer present should be removed as it causes failure of component due to pores and crack initiation. The micro abrasive machine proves to be a cost effective machining process for surface integrity improvement of EDM components. Micro abrasive jet machining is a non-traditional machining process in which a high pressure air stream and abrasive particles are impinged on a work surface through a nozzle. The micro abrasive jet machining enables the removal of the recast layer and is suitable for micro mechanical components. The air pressure, abrasive size and nozzle tip distance are considered as controlling parameters. The effect of each controlling parameter on maximum thickness removal and minimal surface roughness is analysed. Principal component analysis was carried out for the optimisation of the process.

Index Terms—micro abrasive jet machining, robotic micro machining, EDM, recast layer removal, principal component analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

EDM has been used for decades to manufacture precision components including crucial aerospace engine, fuel system, and landing- gear components, as well as other high-stress, high-temperature parts. The EDM process, which generates small cutting force, is ideal to machine micro features [1, 2]. Throughout its history, however, the surface integrity of EDM-machined components has been questioned. As a result, manufacturers tightened their specifications on spark eroded parts, requiring post-EDM secondary processing such as machining and chemical etching, or both. The manufacturers identified the damage caused by EDM which is an electro-thermal process. This damage was a result of the heat generated by the EDM process, and consisted of the recast layer, or white layer, and an annealed Heat Affected Zone (HAZ), which lay directly below the hard recast layer. The recast layer is made up of molten metal particles that have been re-deposited onto the surface of the workpiece. Both the HAZ and recast layer could also contain micro-cracks that could cause stress failures of critical components. As a result of these concerns, manufacturers either developed or revised specifications on the use of EDM to manufacture micro

components. Hence it is inevitable to remove the recast layer to ensure quality of EDM machined components. This requirement added an extra step in the manufacturing process, increasing delivery times, as well as adding extra costs related to more processes and hazardous waste disposal.

Micro abrasive jet machining (μ AJM) has been used extensively for surface improvement. Micro abrasive jet machining using fine abrasive media is particularly suitable for microfabrication and surface treatment of micro mechanical components [3]. In contrast to conventional erosion by large-scale particles, no strength degradation occurs on the micro-machined surfaces [4]. The fine abrasive carried by adequately high air pressure enables the Micro abrasive jet machining process to modify the EDM surface on micro mechanical components. The machining thickness for recast layer range from 5-20 microns. Manual μ AJM is time consuming and the product is having complex structure which makes difficulty in manual machining. Hence an automated micro abrasive jet machine is developed for the purpose of recast layer removal. The schematic of μ AJM is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of Robotic micro abrasive jet machining

II. AUTOMATED MICRO ABRASIVE JET MACHINE

Automated Micro-Abrasive Jet Machine mainly consists of six components namely Micro Blasters, Air Dryers, Dust Collectors, Nozzles, Abrasive Media and a robot.

Here Dual Tank MB 1002 with operating pressure up to 8.6 bar is used. Direct flow Micro Blaster DF1400 equipped with powder gate and modulator is used. Main use of Dual Tank Micro Blaster is that it allows to switch over two different abrasives with separate hoses and handpicks without cross contamination. Direct Flow Micro Blaster, Model: DF1400, is equipped with Powder Gate instead of Conventional Pinch mechanism. It has multiple nozzle capability and improved pneumatic, tubing and fittings and is easier to operate and maintain. The modulator insures consistent media flow by accurately metering the abrasive in the air stream with a minimum of mobbing parts.

Two types of Air Dryers are available namely Desiccant Air Dryer – AD5100 and Continuous Duty Membrane Dryer – AD5300. Here Desiccant Air Dryer – AD5100 is used. It is widely recommended for single micro-abrasive blaster like MB1000 series with low and intermittent use. It contains Silica Gel desiccant beads that absorb moisture to dew points as low as -25°F . It has a Pre-Filter, Pre-Oil Filter to remove the moisture and oil before reaching the desiccant chamber.

A DC2 series dust collector provided by the COMCO Company was used here. This was used to evacuate the abrasives that fly off during machining process. The DC2 is designed to connect to the back of WorkStation through a four-inch flexible duct. The compact size of the DC2 allows it to be located next to the bench on which the WorkStation is located. As air and abrasive are pulled through the filter, the surface of the filter bags trap dust particles. Clean air then passes through the filter and re-circulates into the room. A manual shaker dislodges dust particles from the filter bags and drops them into a drawer for easy disposal. This cloth bag style dust collector will give years of uninterrupted, trouble free service.

An integral part of any micro-abrasive jet machining system; nozzles provide focus and acceleration to the abrasive stream generated by the blaster. An extensive range of nozzle shapes and sizes are available to facilitate different applications. As dry air and abrasive powder pass through the nozzle, they are channeled into a concentrated pattern that enhances the cutting abilities of the specific media and the precision of the process itself. Straight Round Nozzles of size 0.25mm, 0.38mm, 0.46mm and 0.64 mm is used here.

Aluminum oxide is the most commonly used cutting abrasive. The shape and hardness of the particle make it an excellent choice when working with metals or hard brittle parts. Common uses for aluminium oxide include cutting, deburring and the preparation of surfaces. It is available in a wide range of sizes from 10 to 150 microns.

IRB120 is ABB's smallest ever multipurpose industrial robot that weighs just 25kg and can handle a payload of 3kg (4kg for vertical wrist) with a reach of 580mm. It is a cost-effective and reliable choice for generating high production outputs in return for low investment. The IRB 120 is the benchmark for rapid applications requiring extreme flexibility

combined with industry leading 10 micron repeatability. While keeping its trademark compact, agile and lightweight features, the six-axis IRB 120 variant delivers a substantial increase in the maximum speeds of axis 4,5 and 6, resulting in cycle time improvements of up to 25%. IRC5 compact controller is used for the IRB120 robot. The IRC5 compact is a smaller version of the IRC5. It is a robot controller from ABB that employs the TrueMove and QuickMove technologies, which give the robot its accuracy, speed, cycle-time, as well as external device synchronization and configuration. It uses FlexPendant programming RAPID language, and dynamic communication abilities all in a smaller body. It also utilizes a 220/230 V power supply at 50/60 Hz of frequency, and weighs 28.5 kilograms in a 258 x 450 x 580 body. The two fixtures were made for the work holding and for the nozzle holding. The Robotic μ AJM setup is shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Robotic μ AJM setup

III. EXPERIMENTATION

The present work aimed at optimizing thickness removed and surface roughness produced in the micro-abrasive jet machining process. These two are the important factors to be taken care of during the micro-abrasive jet machining. The effect of four process parameters, namely, Abrasive size, Pressure, stand off Distance (SOD) and Feed Rate, was studied on robotic Micro-abrasive jet machining process as shown in Table I. The L9 orthogonal array was used in performing the experiment. There were nine set of experiments and the combination of parameters were selected according to the L9 Orthogonal array. A specimen for experimentation was made with nine projections on maraging steel. The experimental result is shown in Table II. The abrasive size and pressure were varied in Comco machine while the standoff distance and feed rate were varied with help of the robot. The thickness removed (TR) was measured using micro height gauge and surface roughness (SR) using Talysurf. From the results optimisation is to be carried out for maximum thickness removal and

minimum surface roughness value. This is performed using the principal component analysis for multi parameter optimisation.

TABLE I. CONTROL PARAMETERS

Factors	Levels		
	1	2	3
Abrasive Size Microns	50	25	10
Pressure Psi	15	20	25
SOD mm	10	15	20
Feed Rate mm/s	2.5	5	7.5

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

No	Abrasive Size, μm	Pressure, Psi	SOD, mm	Feed Rate, mm/s	TR, μm	SR, μm
1	50	15	10	2.5	9	0.3927
2	50	20	15	5	16	0.4911
3	50	25	20	7.5	10	0.558
4	25	15	15	7.5	6	0.2053
5	25	20	20	2.5	16	0.2338
6	25	25	10	5	8	0.2173
7	10	15	20	5	4	0.2609
8	10	20	10	7.5	7	0.253
9	10	25	15	2.5	15	0.2853

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Principal component analysis (PCA) involves a mathematical procedure that transforms a number of possibly correlated variables into a smaller number of uncorrelated variables called principal components. The first principal component accounts for as much of the variability in the data as possible, and each succeeding component accounts for as much of the remaining variability as possible. Depending on the field of application, it is also named the discrete Karhunen–Loève transform (KLT), the Hotelling transform or proper orthogonal decomposition (POD). Principal component analysis (PCA) was introduced in 1901 by Pearson [5] and further developed by Hotelling [6]. Now it is mostly used as a tool in exploratory data analysis and for making predictive models. PCA involves the calculation of the eigenvalue

decomposition of a data covariance matrix or singular value decomposition of a data matrix, usually after mean centering the data for each attribute. The results of a PCA are usually discussed in terms of component scores and loadings.

Principal component analysis is a multivariate statistical method, which allows the representation of the original dataset in a new reference system characterized by new variables called principal components. Each principal component has the property of explaining the maximum possible amount of variance obtained in the original dataset. PCA can thus gather highly correlated independent variables into a principal component and all principal components are independent of each other. All it does is to transform a set of correlated variables to a set of uncorrelated principal components. A weighting factor for a principal component is determined based on its contribution percentage to total variance. Then, for multiple objectives the index can be formulated by integrating all principal components through the weighting methods. The procedure of PCA is as follows:

The first step in the PCA analysis is to preprocess data in order to normalize the raw data for the analysis. This process is known as grey relational generation. The output process parameters are normalized depending upon their behavioral aspect i.e. surface roughness should be as low as possible whereas material removal rate should be as high as possible. So, to normalize various parameters depending on their nature, equations below are used.

$$Z_i = 1 - [X_i^*/\max(X_i)] \text{ higher the better} \quad (1)$$

$$Z_i = 1 - [\min(X_i)/X_i^*] \text{ lower the better} \quad (2)$$

Where Z_i is the normalized value; X_i^* is the current value; $\min(X_i)$ and $\max(X_i)$ are the minima and maxima values, the correlation array is obtained as

$$R_{ji} = \frac{\text{Cov}(x_i(j), x_i(l))}{\sigma_{x_i(j)} \sigma_{x_i(l)}} \quad (3)$$

Where, $J=1,2,\dots,n$; $L=1,2,\dots,n$. $\text{Cov}(x_i(j), x_i(l))$ is the covariance of sequences $x_i(j)$ and $x_i(l)$ $\sigma_{x_i(j)}, \sigma_{x_i(l)}$ is the standard deviation of sequence $x_i(j)$ and $x_i(l)$ respectively.

The Eigen values and eigenvectors are determined from the correlation coefficient array,

$$(R - \lambda_k I_m) V_{ik} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where, λ_k Eigen values $\sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k = n$, $k=1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; $V_{ik} = [a_{k1} \ a_{k2} \ \dots \ a_{kn}]$ is the eigenvector corresponding to the Eigen value.

In the next step, principle components are calculated using

$$Z_{mk} = \sum_{i=1}^n x_m(i) \cdot V_{ik} \quad (5)$$

Where, Z_{m1} is called the first principal component, Z_{m2} is called the second principal component and so on. V relates to

[11] Wolak, J.: Parameters affecting the velocity of particle in an abrasive jet, Journal of Engineering Material Technology, 99H, 1977.

[12] Dr. A. k. Paul and R. K. Roy: Some studies on Abrasive jet machining, Journal of the Institution of Engineers (India), Vol 68, part PE 2, November 1987